

Postoperative Epidural Analgesia between 0.25% Ropivacaine Plus Tramadol and 0.25% Bupivacaine Plus Tramadol in Abdominal and lower Limb Surgeries – A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Effective postoperative pain management is crucial for recovery after abdominal and lower limb surgeries. Epidural analgesia, using ropivacaine or bupivacaine, is common, with ropivacaine often paired with tramadol to improve pain relief while minimizing side effects. This study compares the efficacy and safety of 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol versus 0.25% bupivacaine.

Methodology: A prospective observational study of 120 adult patients undergoing elective abdominal or lower limb surgeries. Patients were divided into two groups: one received 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol, the other 0.25% bupivacaine. Pain was assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) at 1, 4-, 8-, 12-, and 24-hours post-surgery. Side effects were also evaluated.

Results: The ropivacaine plus tramadol group had significantly lower pain scores at 1 and 4 hours ($p < 0.05$). Pain levels were similar at later time points. Nausea and vomiting were significantly lower in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group ($p < 0.05$), with no significant difference in other side effects.

Conclusion: Ropivacaine plus tramadol offers better early postoperative pain control and fewer side effects than bupivacaine, while both regimens are effective for longer-term pain management.

Recommendation: Ropivacaine plus tramadol is recommended for better early pain relief and fewer opioid-related side effects.

Keywords: Postoperative Pain, Epidural Analgesia, Ropivacaine, Bupivacaine, Tramadol, Surgery, Pain Management.

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Introduction

Effective postoperative pain management is crucial for enhancing recovery and improving outcomes in patients undergoing surgery [1]. Among the various methods available, epidural analgesia has gained widespread recognition as a particularly effective approach for managing pain, especially in abdominal and lower limb surgeries [2]. These types of procedures are associated with significant postoperative discomfort, which can hinder recovery, impair mobility, and increase the risk of complications such as deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged hospital stays. Effective pain control through epidural analgesia not only improves patient comfort but also facilitates earlier mobilization and faster recovery. It is also associated with a reduction in the use of systemic opioids, thereby minimizing opioid-

related side effects such as nausea, vomiting, and respiratory depression [3,4].

The selection of the appropriate analgesic solution is pivotal in determining the efficacy and safety of epidural analgesia. Local anesthetics, combined with opioids, are the cornerstone of this technique. Among the commonly used local anesthetics for epidural administration, ropivacaine and bupivacaine are prominent due to their potent sensory blockade properties. Both agents are amide-type local anesthetics and share similar chemical structures, yet they differ in their pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic properties [5,6].

Bupivacaine, long regarded as the gold standard for epidural analgesia, is known for its powerful analgesic effects. However, it carries a risk of

cardiovascular toxicity, particularly when used in higher doses or inadvertently

ly administered intravenously. This can manifest as bradycardia, hypotension, or even more severe cardiac arrhythmias. Furthermore, bupivacaine can lead to significant motor blockade, which delays patient mobilization and prolongs recovery time [7,8].

Ropivacaine, a newer agent, was developed to overcome some of these limitations. Structurally similar to bupivacaine, it provides comparable sensory blockade but with a lower propensity for motor blockade and cardiotoxicity [9]. Studies have shown that ropivacaine is associated with less impact on motor function, allowing patients to mobilize earlier, which is critical for reducing postoperative complications such as deep vein thrombosis. Additionally, ropivacaine's safer cardiovascular profile makes it an attractive alternative, particularly in high-risk patients [10,11].

In many clinical settings, local anesthetics are combined with opioids to enhance the analgesic effect of epidural anesthesia. Tramadol, a centrally acting synthetic opioid, is commonly used in combination with ropivacaine or bupivacaine to further improve pain relief [12]. Unlike traditional opioids, tramadol has a dual mechanism of action, working both as a weak mu-opioid receptor agonist and an inhibitor of norepinephrine and serotonin reuptake, thus providing a multimodal approach to pain management. This results in better pain control without the severe side effects commonly associated with stronger opioids, such as respiratory depression, making it a favorable option in postoperative pain management [13,14].

Despite the widespread use of both ropivacaine and bupivacaine in epidural analgesia, there is ongoing debate regarding the optimal choice between the two, particularly when combined with adjuvants like tramadol. While both drugs are effective, their differing side effect profiles may influence clinical decision-making. Ropivacaine's advantages in reducing motor impairment and cardiovascular risks are well documented, but bupivacaine's long-standing role as a potent analgesic continues to make it a popular choice in many surgical settings [15,16].

The aim of this study is to provide a detailed comparison of the effectiveness and safety of these two commonly used combinations of local anesthetics: 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol versus 0.25% bupivacaine alone for postoperative epidural analgesia in abdominal and lower limb surgeries. By evaluating key outcomes such as pain relief, side effects, and functional recovery, this study seeks to offer evidence-based guidance on the optimal regimen for managing postoperative

pain. Ultimately, the results will contribute to better pain management strategies, leading to enhanced patient recovery and improved surgical outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study designed to compare the efficacy and safety of 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol versus 0.25% bupivacaine plus tramadol for postoperative epidural analgesia in patients undergoing abdominal and lower limb surgeries.

Study Setting: The research was conducted in the Surgery and Orthopaedic Operation Theatre complex at MGM Medical College and LSK Hospital in Kishanganj, from June 2023 to July 2024.

Participants: The study enrolled a total of 120 patients, divided into two groups based on the analgesic received.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria consisted of adults aged 18 to 65, classified within ASA physical categories I to III, scheduled for elective abdominal or lower limb surgery requiring epidural analgesia. Exclusion criteria included patients with local infections, coagulopathy, or allergies to study medications which would contraindicate the use of epidural analgesia.

Bias: To address potential sources of bias, healthcare personnel collecting postoperative data were blinded to the patients' treatment group assignments. This blinding was intended to prevent observer bias in the assessment of outcomes.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected at predetermined postoperative time points (1, 4, 8, 12, and 24 hours). The primary measure was pain intensity, assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). Secondary measures included the recording of side effects such as nausea, vomiting, pruritus, and motor weakness. Data were consistently collected by healthcare personnel trained in the methodology and blinded to the treatment allocation to ensure uniformity and reliability.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. Continuous variables were compared using independent t-tests, while categorical data were analyzed using chi-square tests. These analyses were used to assess differences in pain scores and side effects between the treatment groups.

Ethical Considerations: The study was conducted in accordance with ethical principles derived from the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Institutional Review Board of MGM Medical College and LSK Hospital. All participants

provided written informed consent before enrollment in the study. Measures were taken to ensure confidentiality and the ethical handling of patient data throughout the study period.

Results

The prospective observational study involved a total of 120 participants, equally divided into two treatment groups: one receiving 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol and the other receiving 0.25% bupivacaine. The primary outcome measure was the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) pain intensity recorded at 1, 4-, 8-, 12-, and 24-hours post-operation. The results demonstrated a statistically significant lower pain score in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group compared to the bupivacaine group at the 1-hour and 4-hour intervals ($p < 0.05$), indicating more effective pain control with

ropivacaine and tramadol. At subsequent time points (8, 12, and 24 hours), the differences were not statistically significant.

Secondary outcomes included side effects such as nausea, vomiting, pruritus, and motor weakness. The incidence of nausea and vomiting was statistically lower in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group compared to the bupivacaine group ($p < 0.05$). Pruritus and motor weakness did not show significant differences between the groups. The data from this study suggest that 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol provides more effective early postoperative pain relief and reduces the incidence of nausea and vomiting compared to 0.25% bupivacaine alone. These findings could help guide postoperative analgesic choices in clinical settings, emphasizing the need for tailored pain management strategies to enhance patient recovery.

Table 1: Pain Intensity Scores (VAS)

Time Point (hours)	Ropivacaine + Tramadol (Mean \pm SD)	Bupivacaine + Tramadol (Mean \pm SD)	P-value
1	2.5 \pm 0.8	3.6 \pm 0.9	0.032
4	2.9 \pm 0.7	3.8 \pm 0.8	0.045
8	3.4 \pm 0.9	3.5 \pm 1.0	0.780
12	3.2 \pm 0.8	3.3 \pm 0.9	0.625
24	2.8 \pm 0.7	2.9 \pm 0.8	0.550

This table displays the mean VAS pain scores with standard deviations for each treatment group at designated postoperative time points. The P-values indicate the statistical significance of differences between the groups at each time point.

Table 2: Incidence of Side Effects

Side Effect	Ropivacaine + Tramadol (%)	Bupivacaine + Tramadol (%)	P-value
Nausea	18%	32%	0.037
Vomiting	12%	25%	0.046
Pruritus	15%	14%	0.890
Motor Weakness	10%	11%	0.910

This table lists the percentages of patients experiencing each listed side effect in the two groups. Chi-square tests are used to determine the significance of differences in the incidence of each side effect between groups.

Discussion

This prospective observational study compared the efficacy and safety of 0.25% ropivacaine plus tramadol with 0.25% bupivacaine for postoperative epidural analgesia in patients undergoing abdominal and lower limb surgeries. The key findings revealed that the combination of ropivacaine plus tramadol resulted in significantly lower pain intensity scores in the early postoperative period, specifically at the 1-hour and 4-hour time points. After 8, 12, and 24 hours, the pain scores in both groups were similar, with no statistically significant differences. Additionally, the incidence of nausea and vomiting was significantly lower in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group, while the occurrence of other side effects,

such as pruritus and motor weakness, was comparable between the two groups.

These results suggest that 0.25% ropivacaine combined with tramadol offers superior analgesic efficacy during the early postoperative period compared to 0.25% bupivacaine alone. The enhanced pain relief at 1- and 4-hours post-surgery indicates that ropivacaine with tramadol provides faster and more effective control of postoperative pain, which is crucial for patient comfort and recovery in the immediate post-surgical phase. This effect appears to taper off over time, as pain scores between the two groups become similar after 8 hours, suggesting that both regimens are comparably effective for sustained pain control beyond the early postoperative period.

The significant reduction in nausea and vomiting observed in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group is another key finding. These side effects are common in postoperative patients, particularly with the use of opioids, and their reduction is a major advantage

for improving overall patient outcomes [17]. By reducing the incidence of these complications, the ropivacaine and tramadol combination may help improve patient comfort, reduce the need for additional antiemetic medications, and facilitate faster recovery [18].

These findings align with previous studies that have explored the analgesic benefits of combining tramadol with local anesthetics like ropivacaine. Several studies have demonstrated that tramadol, when used as an adjunct in epidural analgesia, enhances the analgesic effect of local anesthetics without significantly increasing adverse events. Tramadol's unique mechanism of action, involving both opioid and monoaminergic pathways, is thought to provide a synergistic effect when used in combination with local anesthetics. The findings of this study further corroborate these conclusions, as the combination of tramadol with ropivacaine resulted in better pain control than bupivacaine alone during the critical early hours after surgery [19,20].

Comparisons with previous studies evaluating ropivacaine and bupivacaine as sole agents have also demonstrated that ropivacaine offers a better safety profile, particularly with respect to motor blockade [21]. In our study, although motor weakness was assessed as a secondary outcome, the similar incidence rates between the two groups suggest that the addition of tramadol to ropivacaine does not increase the likelihood of motor impairment. This is consistent with existing research indicating that ropivacaine has a lower propensity for motor block than bupivacaine, making it a preferable choice for patients requiring early mobility post-surgery [22,23].

The lower incidence of nausea and vomiting in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group is noteworthy, particularly in light of previous studies demonstrating that tramadol has a lower emetogenic potential than other opioids [24]. This contrasts with bupivacaine's reliance on stronger opioids for effective pain management, which may contribute to a higher incidence of gastrointestinal side effects. Our results suggest that by reducing the need for additional opioid administration, the ropivacaine plus tramadol combination could decrease opioid-related adverse effects, thereby enhancing overall patient well-being [25].

The superior analgesic efficacy of ropivacaine plus tramadol in the early postoperative period can be explained by the synergistic mechanisms of action of the two drugs. Ropivacaine, a long-acting amide local anesthetic, provides sensory blockade by inhibiting sodium ion channels in neuronal membranes, thus preventing the propagation of pain signals [26]. Tramadol, a centrally acting analgesic, exerts its effects through a dual

mechanism: weak opioid receptor agonism and inhibition of serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake. This multimodal action of tramadol enhances its analgesic efficacy and complements the local anesthetic effects of ropivacaine. The combination of these drugs likely provides a more potent and prolonged analgesic effect, particularly in the immediate postoperative period when pain is typically most intense [27,28].

The lower incidence of nausea and vomiting in the ropivacaine plus tramadol group can be attributed to the fact that tramadol has a milder side effect profile compared to traditional opioids like morphine or fentanyl, which are commonly used alongside bupivacaine for postoperative pain control [29]. Tramadol's partial agonist properties and its monoaminergic effects likely contribute to the reduced occurrence of gastrointestinal side effects. By reducing the reliance on stronger opioids, the combination of ropivacaine and tramadol minimizes opioid-induced nausea and vomiting, thus offering an additional benefit in terms of patient comfort [30].

Moreover, the similar incidence of pruritus and motor weakness between the two groups further supports the safety of using tramadol in combination with ropivacaine. While tramadol has been associated with pruritus in some cases, the absence of significant differences in this side effect suggests that it does not exacerbate the risk when used in this context. The comparable rates of motor weakness reinforce the known safety profile of ropivacaine, which is associated with lower motor blockade compared to bupivacaine [25].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the combination of 0.25% ropivacaine with tramadol offers more effective pain relief in the early postoperative period and reduces the incidence of nausea and vomiting compared to 0.25% bupivacaine. These findings highlight the potential of this combination to enhance postoperative analgesia, particularly in the crucial early hours after surgery, while minimizing common opioid-related side effects. The results align with previous research and provide a strong rationale for considering the use of ropivacaine with tramadol as a preferred option for epidural analgesia in abdominal and lower limb surgeries. This approach not only improves pain control but also contributes to better overall patient outcomes by reducing complications and enhancing recovery.

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